

Individual and Institutional Determinants of Trainees' Enrolment in Public Technical Vocational Education and Training Institutions in Nakuru County, Kenya

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study was to investigate the individual and institutional determinants of trainee enrolment in public, technical vocational, education and training (TVET) institutions in Nakuru County, Kenya. The study was informed by the large number of secondary school graduates idling in the community and efforts of government of Kenya to raise enrolment in TVETs for skill training to actualise vision 2030. The study sought to investigate whether trainees' attitude had influence on enrolment in public TVETs in Nakuru County, Kenya. The study was guided by the Social Learning Theory of Career Decision Making (SLTCMD) by John D. Krumboltz (1976). The theory focuses on developing career readiness through implementation of learning theory in school-to-work programs. This study employed descriptive survey research design. The sample size consisted of 12 TVETs, 30 trainers and 331 trainees drawn from the target population of 24 public TVETs, 150 trainers and 2385 trainees from entire Nakuru County. Data was collected by use of interview schedule for the TVET principals, questionnaires for trainers and trainees and document analysis. Data were processed and analysed qualitatively and quantitatively. Descriptive statistics which included frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviations were generated and used in presenting research findings. Statistical tests were done using correlation coefficient and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) at 95% confidence interval of the difference ($\alpha=0.05$) to be sure true mean is used. The findings of the correlation between trainees' attitudes and enrolment in TVETs showed that, P value was $0.3883 > P=0.05$, therefore H_0 was accepted and a conclusion made that there was no significant relationship between trainees' attitudes and enrolment of trainees. Based on the findings, the study concluded that, trainees' attitudes do not negatively influence enrolment in TVETs since the trainees willingly chose to enroll in TVETs regardless of the negative publicity towards TVETs. The researcher recommended that, these trainees who have experienced the benefits of enrolling in TVET, to be good ambassadors in their communities so as to change the image of TVETs' negative publicity so that more prospective trainees enroll which could result to increased enrolment.

KEY WORDS: Enrolment, Institutional and Individual Determinants, Prospective Trainees, Technical Vocational Education and Training, Trainees' Attitudes

INTRODUCTION

Education and training is a key supporter of human capital development and an essential human right. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) singled out instruction as key to advancement (UN General Assembly, 2015). The United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) and International Centre for Technical, Vocational Education and Training (TVET) lays emphasis on Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in transforming Education with a vision of ensuring inclusive and quality Education for all and promote lifelong learning. (UNESCO, 2015). The SDG No. 4 on Vocational Training Education requires member states, Kenya included to ensure access to TVET Education programmes, increase training for youth to enable them to get decent jobs, start entrepreneurship outlets and become self-reliant. Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) focuses on providing lifelong skills that meet the needs of the work place, industry and self-employment. A number of developed countries worldwide like Japan, Italy, Sweden Britain and China have funded TVETS heavily, an initiative that has increased chances of the youth who leave school to enroll in the TVET Institutions (Carmago, A., Souza, A., Lima, L &

Soares, J., 2015). However, in developing countries there is inadequate funding for TVETs which limit school leavers from enrolling in TVETs. UNESCO (2013) and Shaibu (2013), cited persistent challenges in enrolment in Technical Education in Nigeria due to poor implementation of policies in relation to TVET funding and resource distribution.

The parents in every community look down on TVET. Consequently, bright students do not enrol in TVET as their parents prioritize paying for academic oriented careers hence TVET becomes the dumping ground for those whose academic capacity is low. According to Mulongo and Kitururu (2016) in their study in Tanzania on determinants for positioning and marketing TVET, students who do not excel in O' Level secondary education are the ones who enroll in TVETs. Since TVETs are viewed as alternative education for those who perform poorly in academics, prospective trainees shy away hence low enrolment in TVETs. Ramhari Lamichhane (2013), Nazier & Muhd (2019) and Okello (2011) all agree with Mulongo and Kitururu (2016) on the fact that TVETs generally enrol trainees who score low grades in secondary education hence negative attitude. Most students are less interested in occupations targeted by TVET courses since they are viewed as occupations of low status. According to Deebom and Zite (2017), in their study carried out in Asian countries on the role and status of TVETs found out that, the students barred from joining other academic disciplines due to their low performance in the secondary level of education are the ones admitted in TVETs. This aspect causes prospective trainees of TVETs to have negative attitude towards TVETs in fear of being seen as low academic achievers.

Kenya is grappling with the situation of few TVET Institutions and perpetual low enrolment. The country has continually enacted legal framework to address Education and Training in Kenya putting more emphasis on TVETs. The constitution of Kenya 2010 and Kenya vision 2030 has placed special demands on the tertiary sector, TVETs included as the leading engine that the economy must rely upon to produce adequate members of middle level professionals needed to drive the economy towards the attainment of the vision. The objective of the Kenya vision 2030 is to make Kenya a newly industrializing, middle income country providing high quality life for all her citizens by the year 2030. To achieve this vision, technological innovation and development is needed hence the need to place emphasis on TVET Education and training so as to produce a critical mass of well qualified technologists and engineers to spur development. National Educational Sector Support Programme (NESSP) has come up with the National Education Sector Strategic Plan (NESSP) 2018-2022, with its elaborate causal chain that provides explicit linkages from programme activities to the NESSP 2018- 2022 strategic objectives that are geared towards achievement of vision 2030. The NESSP 2018-2022 adopts a thematic level planning by sub-sectors, with TVET being one of them to carry out training and skills development in science, technology and innovation for achievement of vision 2030 (MOE-NESSP 2018-2022).

Despite the government efforts on TVETs to attract prospective trainees, negative publicity has dealt a blow to TVETs in many counties in Kenya. Kamau (2013) in his study on challenges affecting technical and vocational training in Kiambu County in Kenya found out that, TVET is seen as a sub-par training choice appropriate for the drop-outs and less astute students. TVET education is seen as low quality education created for low achievers and failures in basic education. Even after enrolling in the TVET institution as a trainee, the trainees would not proudly identify themselves with the TVET (Agodini & Novak, 2014, Kamau, 2013). This has to a greater extent influenced the level of the enrolment by trainees in TVET courses offered in Kenya in fear of being associated with failures in academic performance. To improve on enrolment in TVET, the government of Kenya has taken a number of measures to enhance training. The Kenya 2013 TVET Act, which aims at strengthening the relevance and quality of TVET, has incorporated TVETs with the private sector, to deliver skill acquisition and training (Republic of Kenya, 2013). The constitution of Kenya 2010, section (2) - 9 placed TVET institutions under county governments empowering them to take charge of the institutions while the TVET Bill 2012 contains collection of lawful structures in the TVET and accommodates the foundation of a TVET Authority (TVETA) to supervise the TVET framework. The National Policy for Vocational Training Centres (MoEST, 2014) notes that, vocational education and training is an investment with significant social rate of returns. The Sessional Paper No.1 of 2019, a Policy Framework for Reforming Education and Training for Sustainable Development in Kenya fortified the National Skills Training Strategy and the modification of the legitimate system for TVET Bill whose point was to reinforce the components for the execution of the essential TVET reforms (Republic of Kenya, 2019). These legal documents ensure TVET operations are streamlined to equip trainees with necessary skills. The operationalization of the TVET bill as per the constitution of Kenya requires well trained human resources which do not have to be trained in the universities. The county government, through concerted efforts of TVET institutions can develop and offer training tailored towards ensuring that, the

county government meet their constitutionally delegated mandate of providing immense opportunities for youth training and subsequent youth employment in Kenya (Government of Kenya (2010), Government of Kenya (2020)

Despite County government being empowered to run TVET institutions, in Nakuru County, most of the technical institutions mainly target class eight leavers for skills training development. Information obtained from the Technical Vocational Education and Training County Director in Nakuru County, confirms low enrolment, access and participation (Lang'at, 2015). The TVET county director attributes low enrolment of trainees as a product of the targeted group of those who drop out of primary education and those who perform poorly in secondary education scoring grades that range from C- to E and low remuneration of TVET graduates as compared to academic oriented careers. Records from the Ministry of Education in Nakuru County indicate that, despite TVET institutions having a capacity to accommodate many trainees; total enrolment is low and as a result of negative attitude towards TVETs, prospective trainees enrol for academic oriented careers.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Globally, education and training is recognised as the key to human capital development. Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) offers human capital development through provision of lifelong skills that meet needs of work place, industry and self-employment. Unfortunately, enrolment in TVET institutions worldwide is low, Kenya included and this has caused high percentage of youths legible for training in TVETs remain untrained according to Kenya Universities and Colleges Central Placement Service (KUCCPS) criteria for prequalification based on performance (KNEC, 2021). Nakuru County is reeling with her share of low enrolment since her TVET institutions do not enrol trainees to the capacities they can hold. In addition, the TVET institutions in Nakuru County are few despite the fact that the county is extensive and densely populated. The Nakuru County government in her development plan, 2018-2022 has undertaken to equip existing TVET centres, recruit more trainers and respond to job market needs in a bid to attract prospective trainees to enrol in her institutions. Infrastructure, tools and equipment have been allocated 450 million to be funded by county government, capacity building funds allocated is 12 million and funds for paying for the training fees for the youth allocation is 100 million to be funded by Nakuru County treasury (County Government of Nakuru, 2018). Despite the Nakuru County government's effort to address the gap of low enrolment in her TVET institutions, enrolment has remained low in Nakuru County TVETs putting the idle unemployable youth at risk of indulging in drugs and substance abuse. As a result of this identified gap, this study was conducted to investigate the individual and institutional determinants of trainee enrolment in public, technical vocational education and training institutions in Nakuru County, Kenya, with the aim of increasing enrolment of youth to TVETs so as to equip them with employable and self-employment skills to enable them to be involved in nation building.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study was to investigate the individual and institutional determinants of trainee enrolment in public, technical vocational, education and training institutions in Nakuru County, Kenya

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The study was guided by the following specific objective

To assess the extent to which trainees' attitudes influenced their enrolment in public TVETs in Nakuru County, Kenya.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

In order to test the influence of trainees' attitude on enrolment, a null hypothesis was developed

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between trainees' attitudes and enrolment of trainees' in public TVETs in Nakuru County, Kenya.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is based on the Social Learning Theory of Career Decision Making (SLTCDM). The theory was presented by John D. Krumboltz in 1976. Krumboltz was addressing the concern why people prefer one educational program or occupation to another. This is the same concern being addressed since the preference of educational program or occupation will lead to increased

enrolment where the course is offered for career development. The theory states that, psychological functioning can be explained in terms of the interaction of personal characteristics, previous behaviour (learning) and environmental conditions. Personal characteristics and learning will include the individual determinants which include the attitude of trainees towards enrolling in TVETs, while previous behaviour and environmental conditions explain the institutional determinants like the courses on offer and availability of teaching learning resources. The theory is hence suitable to this study on individual and institutional determinants of trainees' enrolment in TVETs since the prospective trainees will make decision to enrol in TVETs which shall lead them to pursue technical oriented career path.

The social learning theory for career decision making identifies interactions of genetic influence, cognitive processes, emotional processes, environmental conditions' influence and performance skills on people's career choices (Krumboltz & Mitchel, 1990). According to Krumboltz (1976), there are four factors that influence choice of a course or career in this theory which are; Genetic endowment or social abilities consisting of race, sex, physical appearances and physical defects that cannot be changed. This study has the objective of attitude of trainees' influence on enrolment, which is related to emotional processes and environmental conditions which will influence choosing of technical career path leading to enrolment in TVETs, Environmental conditions and events are factors usually outside the control of any individual. They are due to number and nature of job opportunities, training opportunities, social policies and procedures for selecting trainees and family resources. Learning experiences act on the environment to produce certain consequences and associative learning experiences brought by external stimuli and task approach skills are set of skills, performance standards, mental sets and emotional responses that are interactions between emotional, genetic and environmental influences (Krumboltz, Mitchell & Jones, 1976).

The social learning theory of career decision making was used in a study carried out on factors influencing enrolment in urban agricultural education programme in Pennsylvania university by Blannie and Levon (2004). The study sought to determine the individuals influencing students to enroll in an urban agricultural programme and to determine the events or experiences influencing enrolment. This theory is therefore relevant for this study on individual and institutional determinants of trainee enrolment in TVET institutions in that, enrolment in TVETs can be influenced by the attitude of the prospective trainee, the decision on career path to take and external forces like enrolment policy and enrolment process.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Trainees' attitude towards TVET courses and enrolment in TVET institutions

TVET sector is faced with the challenges of negative perception and poor image which has continued over a period of time. The sector is often seen as last choice of education and not a preferred option in education and training. The poor image can be attributed to multiple factors related to equity, access, quality and relevance. Among the factors leading to this negative perception include lack of specialization in TVET Institutions, lack of clear admission and progression procedures, inadequate career guidance in basic education, inappropriate infrastructure and equipment and low funding (MoE-NESSP, 2018).

A research carried out by Saif and Sharjah (2016) in United Emirates on attitudes towards vocational education and training found out that, the general view against Vocational Education is negative and that TVETS are suffering from low reputation and bad image in the society. Reddy and Devi (2011), in their study carried out in India to determine the attitudes of undergraduate students towards vocational education agreed with Saif and Sharjah (2016) that TVETs suffer negative attitude generally discouraging prospective trainees from enrolling in TVETs. In Ghana parents view on vocational education is that vocational skills are not competitive enough for more high income jobs in the labour market and this makes the parents to be wary of encouraging their children to enroll in the TVETs. Negative view in the community discourages prospective trainees from enrolling in the training institutions (Aryeetey & Andoh, 2011). Vocational education is not easily accepted due to the negative attitude and the bad image. Olema (2018) and Buyiaga (2021) in their studies related to gender and vocational courses found that, male students have more positive attitudes towards enrolling in TVETS than female students in Nigeria.

A study carried out by international rescue committee in Malaysia (IRC, 2016) on evaluation of significant factors leading to low enrolment of females in TVET found out that, in particular, training in technical careers is a traditionally male industry, lack of knowledge about the strengths of TVET, in adequate financial support due to low socio-economic status and doubts in the future employment are key reasons why few female trainees are venturing in TVET oriented careers. Similarly Alam & Forhad (2020) in their study carried out in Bangladesh on the same issue of low enrolment argued that some of the factors influencing female

involvement in TVET include low perception of females in society, weak entry level, poor attitude towards TVET, lack of recognition of females in society, sexism towards TVET graduates and elitism.

Ayonmike (2014), Jyot (2012), Chinyere (2014) all concurred in the same direction in their studies on low enrolment of females in TVETS. Ismail (2019) in his study on attitude and performance examined the relationship between the attitude and performance in vocational training centers in Malaysia and found out that, mentality assumed a fundamental role in deciding trainees' enrolment in TVETs. Youthful trainees who enrol in TVET institutions already have framed opinions and attitudes. A portion of these suppositions are socially based (Hansen, 2015). Negative attitude towards vocational education goes back to the pioneer history of Kenya. Academic advancement was seen as having a higher societal position than professional training and even pulled in higher wages in salaried employments, making a feeling of optional specialist for those in specialized fields. This has caused low trainee enrolment in public TVET institutions.

According to Kinyanjui (2007), a negative attitude towards vocational education and training is not just among the community individuals, but on the other hand is showed by educators and trainees as they feel insufficient academically. This acts against viable mentorship from the trainers (Kamau, 2013). This attitude of mind is reinforced by the advancements where specialized technical institutions and National polytechnics are being changed into constituent university colleges and universities to offer non-technical courses (Muindi, 2011). Nevertheless, with the government of Kenya having the policy of 100% transition, new TVET institutions are being registered in the believe that those who score low grades in KCSE will enroll in the institutions. A typical perspective on vocational education and training among numerous individuals is that it is generally meant for students who have a low academic capacity and whose essential expectation is a quick passage to employment or self-employment (Maliranta, Nurmi, & Virtanen, 2010) all agree on this aspect. To help improve the TVET trainees' self-esteem, it is vital to recognize the fundamental point of possessing vocational knowledge is to provide lifelong skills that meet needs of the work place, industry as well as self-employment as opposed to the issue of academic capabilities. Based on the literature reviewed, this study sought to investigate the extend to which trainees' attitude influences enrolment in TVET institutions and thus, this proposed research study intends to fill this gap.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design

This study employed descriptive survey research design. A survey is an attempt to collect data from members of a population in order to determine the status of the population with respect to one or more variables. As a method, descriptive survey ensures collection of numerical data to answer questions about the status of the phenomena under study. The design explored individual and institutional determinants of trainees' enrolment in public TVET institutions. The design was considered appropriate because it was capable of facilitating collection of data that described specific characteristics of phenomena in order to determine the status of a population with respect to one or more variables.

Target population

The study was conducted in all the 24 registered public Technical Vocational Education and Training institutions in Nakuru County that had operated for at least five years and had continually posted low trainees enrolment over the years. The respondents of the proposed study were drawn from these 24 registered public TVETs in the County. The study targeted 24 institutions' principals, 150 trainers and 2,385 trainees (County Director of TVET, 2019). Thus the total population targeted was 2559 respondents.

Sample size and sampling procedure

Cooper and Schindler (2014) define sample size as a smaller set of the larger. According to Gay and Airasian (2003), a sample of 20 percent to 50 percent is recommended for small target groups. Therefore 50 percent of registered public TVETs were randomly sampled to get a sample of twelve TVETs and twelve principals. Twenty percent of the trainers were taken to give a sample size of 30 trainers. Cochran (1977) formula was used to calculate the sample size of trainees. Cochran formula was appropriate for this study because the target population of the study was large. The formula is given as;

$$n_o = \frac{z^2 pq}{e^2}$$

Whereby; n_o is the sample size, z is abscissa of the normal curve that cuts off an area at the tails, p is the estimated proportion of an attribute present in the population, q is $1-p$ and e is the desired level of precision. In this study, $p = 0.5$ (Maximum variability), $q = 1-0.5$, desired confidence level = 95% and level of precision = $\pm 5\%$. Using this formula, with the desired confidence level of 95% and precision level of $\pm 5\%$ the sample size for trainees was given as at least 331 respondents. Therefore, the total sample size was 373 respondents.

Data collection instruments

The tools of data collection for this study were interview schedule for principals, questionnaires for instructors and trainees and document analysis guide. The questionnaires were used for data collection from the trainees because they offered considerable advantages in the administration, presented even stimulus to large numbers of people simultaneously and provided the researcher with an easy accumulation of data. Gay and Airasian (1992) maintain that questionnaires give respondents freedom to express their views or opinion. A document analysis guide allowed collection of secondary data by way of interrogating official records for verification of the situation on the ground.

Data collection procedures

The researcher first sought clearance from the University of Nairobi to apply for a permit from National Commission for Science, Technology and Innovation (NACOSTI). The researcher was licensed to conduct research in Nakuru County for a period of one year from 23rd August 2021 to 23rd August 2022 by license number NACOSTI/P/21/12459 and applicant identification number 235768. The researcher then proceeded to seek further clearance from office of the County Director of Education (CDE) in Nakuru County, County commissioner's office and public service, training and devolution office of Nakuru County on 5th, 6th and 7th October 2021 respectively as per the guidelines of NACOSTI license to seek permission from those relevant authorities. Thereafter the researcher wrote letters to the principals of the sampled TVETs to be allowed to do the study. The selected TVETs were visited to book appointments on when to visit them for data collection. Questionnaires were administered and picked as per the agreement.

Data analysis techniques

This was done by first cleaning, coding, entering and then analyzing. The data was analyzed both qualitatively and quantitatively. Quantitative data was edited to eliminate inconsistencies, summarized and coded for easy classification in order to facilitate tabulation and interpretation. The researcher then used Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) IBM version 20 to analyze data. Descriptive statistics was used in describing the sample data in such a way as to portray the typical respondent and to reveal the general response pattern. Qualitative data analysis was done by describing the distribution of single variables. The relationships and links between the independent and dependent variables were discussed and logical conclusions made. Inferential statistics were used; correlation coefficients and one-way ANOVA test was applied for trainers and trainees output to test the null hypotheses against the alternative hypotheses that not all means are the same, at $\alpha = 0.05$ significance level to test null hypotheses and provide statistical relationship of variables.

Research findings and discussion

Objective - To assess the extent to which trainees' attitudes influenced their enrolment in public TVETs in Nakuru County, Kenya. The researcher looked at in-depth information of the attitude of trainees and how trainees' attitude influenced enrolment in TVETs. Various aspects of relationship between attitude and enrolment were explored. A questionnaire item was constructed to establish the attitude of trainees towards enrolling in TVETs. The responses were presented in figures and frequency tables and percentages.

Influence of trainees' attitude on enrolment in TVET institutions

The study sought to investigate the extent to which trainees' attitude influence enrolment in TVET institutions. Attitude of trainees emanates from trainees' parents or guardians and entire community. Negative attitude lowers enrolment while positive attitude increases enrolment (Buyiaga, 2021). According to Kamau (2013), enrolment in TVETs has been marred by negative

attitude of entire community. The researcher collected data from trainers and trainees to determine how attitude of trainees, parents or guardians and entire community influence enrolment in public TVETs in Nakuru County.

Trainers' views on willingness of trainees' to enroll in TVET institution

The researcher sought to establish from trainers whether trainees willingly enrolled in the TVET institutions. The researcher asked the trainers to indicate their views on the willingness of trainees to enroll in TVET institution and whether they were encouraged to enroll or were discouraged by their parents or guardians and peers. The willingness to enroll freely without being forced or pestered by parents or guardian is an indicator of positive attitude while enrolling as a last result of prevailing circumstances that do not allow enrolling in other tertiary institutions of higher learning depicts negative attitude towards TVETs. The results are summarized in the figure 1

Figure 1. Percentage willingness of trainees to enroll in TVET institutions

Majority of the trainers agreed at 73.33 percent that trainees willingly enrolled in TVETs which was interpreted to mean the attitude of trainees towards TVET institutions was positive while 26.67 percent indicated they were not willing to enroll in TVETs but they had no alternative but to enroll in TVET since they could not be placed in any other institution for various reasons. This group of trainees gave varying explanations why they enrolled in TVET unwillingly. One reason which was common was that the grade scored in KCSE was low and they could not get a suitable course elsewhere so they had to enroll in TVET where their grade is relevant. Another reason given was that, the parents or guardians could only afford to maintain them in the TVET due to proximity of the institution to their home hence reduced cost in terms of transport and subsistence. These were indicators of negative attitude. This means that, even though majority had positive attitude, enrolment was not increasing therefore something needs to be done to portray the positive attitude claim. It could mean that low enrolment is not attributed to negative attitude to some extent but could be due to other unforeseen determinants of enrolment from the trainees' point of view and parents or guardians of trainees. These findings concur with research carried out by Saif and Sharjah (2016) in United Emirates on attitudes towards vocational education and training which found out that, the general view against Vocational Education is negative and that TVETS are suffering from low reputation and bad image in the society as it was opined by Reddy and Devi (2011) in their research also in India.

Trainers’ views on influence of trainees’ attitude on enrolment

The trainers gave their responses on the items concerning attitude of trainees towards TVETs as the researcher needed to establish the same. The trainers’ responses are summarized in table 1

Table 1. Trainers’ view of influence of trainee’s attitude on enrolment in TVETs

	Mean	Std. Dev.	SA %	A %	D %	SD %
Trainees prefer theoretical work to practical work	3.2667	.52083	0.00	3.3	66.7	30.0
Given the opportunity to join academic oriented courses, trainees would not have enrolled in TVET	2.1333	1.07425	36.7	26.7	23.3	13.3
Trainees enrolled in the TVET to gain skills for self-employment	1.8333	.46113	20.0	76.7	3.3	0.00
TVETs are dumping grounds for school drop outs	2.7667	.93526	0.00	56.7	10.0	33.3
TVETs are institutes for accommodating children of the poor	2.5000	.86103	3.3	63.3	13.3	20.0
TVETs are institutions for pre occupying the youth	2.3333	.95893	13.3	60.0	6.7	20.0
TVETs are good for non-performers in academics	2.6000	1.06997	13.3	43.3	13.3	30.0
Parents encourage their children to join TVETs	1.7333	.82768	43.3	46.7	3.3	6.7
Parents are aware of the presence of the TVETs and courses offered	1.6667	.84418	50.0	40.0	3.3	6.7

The descriptive statistics results shown in table 1 reveal that trainers disagreed at 66.7 percent that trainees prefer theoretical work to practical work, 30.0 percent of them strongly disagreed and 3.3 percent agreed. The item had a mean rating of 3.2667 and standard deviation of 0.52083. The implication is that majority of the respondents feel that trainees do not prefer theoretical work to practical work. TVET courses should be practical oriented to enable trainees gain real time skills that will assist them to be competitive in the market.

The descriptive statistics results also indicate that trainers strongly agree at 36.7 percent that trainees given opportunity to enroll in academic oriented courses, they would not have enrolled in TVET, 26.7 percent of them agreed, while those who disagreed at 23.3 percent and 13.3 percent strongly disagreed. The item had a mean of 2.1333 and a standard deviation of 1.07425. Therefore, the descriptive statistics results made a conclusion that those trainees given opportunity to join academic oriented courses, they would not have enrolled in TVET. This conclusion clearly shows that, the trainees enrolled in TVET as a last result either due to the low grades attained in secondary level or financial constraints that could not afford paying for education in other learning institutions. The findings are in line with the study carried out by Ismail (2019) in his study on attitude and performance where he examined the relationship between the attitude and performance in vocational training centers in Malaysia and found out that, mentality assumed a fundamental role in deciding students' enrolment in TVETs. Youthful trainees who enrolled in TVET institutions already had framed opinions and attitudes. A portion of these suppositions are socially based (Hansen, 2015) and emanate from the interactions within the community and the view that most students are less interested in occupations targeted by TVET courses since they are viewed as occupations of low status. Deebom and Zite (2017), in their study carried out in Asian countries on the role and status of TVETs found out that, the students barred from enrolling in other academic disciplines due to their low performance in the secondary level of education are the ones admitted in TVETs. This aspect causes prospective trainees of TVETs to have negative attitude towards TVETs in fear of being seen as low academic achievers.

The descriptive analysis results shown in table 1 indicate that 76.7 percent of the trainers agree that trainees enrolled in the TVET to gain skills for self - employment. Those strongly agreed as represented by 20.0 percent and 3.3 percent representing those who disagreed. The item had a mean of 1.8333 and a standard deviation of 0.46113. Therefore, most of the informants indicated that trainees do not enroll in the TVET to gain skills for self – employment. This could be the reason why there are few trainees enrolling in TVETs. May be the trainees enroll to gain skills for self-employment and they graduate from the TVETs unable to self-employ themselves hence taint the image of TVETS.

The results indicate that respondents at 56.7 percent of informants agreed that the trainees enrolled in the TVET because they dropped out of school, 33.3 percent strongly disagreed and 10.0 percent disagreed. The item had a mean of 2.7667 and a standard deviation of 0.93526 indicating that majority of the respondents feel that the trainees do not enroll in the TVET because they dropped out of school. Enrolling in TVET is a decision that needs to be keenly looked at since it seems low enrolment can be attributed to factors other than dropping out of school.

The descriptive statistics results shown in table 1 reveal that respondents agreed at 63.3 percent that trainees enrolled in the TVET because they come from a poor family, 20.0 percent of them strongly disagreed, 13.3 percent disagreed while those who strongly agreed at 3.3. The item had a mean rating of 2.5000 and standard deviation of 0.86103 an implication that majority of the respondents feel that trainees do not enroll in the TVET because they come from a poor family.

The descriptive statistics results also indicate that respondents agree at 60.0 percent that trainees joined TVET to be preoccupied and grow, 20.0 percent of them strongly disagreed, while those who strongly agreed at 13.3 percent and 6.7 percent disagreed. The item had a mean of 2.3333 and a standard deviation of 0.95893. Therefore, the descriptive statistics results lead to a conclusion that the trainees do not join TVET to be preoccupied and grow. There is more to being preoccupied and growing when a trainee joins TVET.

The descriptive analysis results shown in table 1 indicate that 43.3 percent of the respondents agree that trainees joined TVET because of performing poorly in school. The respondents who strongly disagreed were represented by 30.0 percent, 13.3 percent representing those both who strongly agreed and disagreed. The item had a mean of 2.600 and a standard deviation of 1.06997. Therefore, most of the informants indicated that trainees do not join TVET because they performed poorly in school.

The results indicate that respondents at 46.7 percent of informants agreed that trainees were encouraged by my parents to join TVET, 43.3 percent strongly agreed, and 6.7 percent strongly disagreed while those who disagreed at 3.3. The item had a mean of 1.7333 and a standard deviation of 0.82768 an indication that majority of the respondents feel trainees were encouraged by their parents to join TVET. Parents help their children to be self-reliant hence encourage taking a course that leads to a particular career.

The results indicate that respondents at 50.0 percent of informants strongly agreed that trainees parents are aware of the presence of the TVETs and courses offered, 40.0 percent agreed, and 6.7 percent strongly disagreed while those who disagreed at 3.3. The item had a mean of 1.6667 and a standard deviation of 0.84418 indicating that majority of the respondents feel that trainees parents are not aware of the presence of the TVETs and courses offered.

Trainees' responses on influence of attitude on enrolment in TVET institutions

The researcher sought to know how trainees' attitude influenced enrolment in TVETs. An item was presented to the respondents to establish the same. The findings were presented in Table 2 for the responses obtained from the items presented to the respondents.

Table 2. Influence of trainee’s attitude on enrolment in TVET Institutions

	Mean	Std. Dev.	SA %	A %	D %	SD %
As a trainee I prefer theoretical work to practical work	2.396	1.0943	28.7	21.1	30.2	19.0
Given opportunity to join academic oriented courses, I would not have enrolled in TVET	2.302	.8630	16.6	46.5	26.9	10.0
I enrolled in the TVET to gain skills for self - employment	1.852	.8630	40.5	39.0	15.4	5.1
I enrolled in the TVET because i dropped out of school	3.468	.7870	4.5	4.8	29.9	60.7
I enrolled in the TVET because I come from a poor family	2.634	1.1609	22.7	24.2	20.2	32.9
I joined TVET to be preoccupied and grow	3.326	1.0310	11.2	8.5	16.9	63.4
I joined TVET because i performed poor in school	3.447	.8975	6.0	9.7	17.8	66.5
I was encouraged by my parents to join TVET	2.417	.9977	21.5	31.4	31.1	16.0
Our parents are aware of the presence of the TVETs and courses offered	1.955	.9508	40.8	29.6	23.0	6.6

The descriptive statistics results shown in table 2 revealed that trainees disagreed at 30.2 percent that as a trainee they prefer theoretical work to practical work, 28.7 percent of them strongly agreed, 22.1 percent agreed while those who strongly disagreed at 19.0. The item had a mean rating of 2.396 and standard deviation of 1.0943 an implication that majority of the respondents feel that as a trainee they do not prefer theoretical work to practical work.

The descriptive statistics results also indicate that respondents agree at 46.5 percent that given opportunity to join academic oriented courses, they would not have enrolled in TVET, 26.9 percent of them disagreed, while those who strongly agreed at 16.6 percent and 10.0 percent strongly disagreed. The item had a mean of 2.302 and a standard deviation of 0.8630. Therefore, the descriptive statistics results making a conclusion that given opportunity to join academic oriented courses, they would not have enrolled in TVET

The descriptive analysis results shown in Table 2 indicate that 40.5 percent of the respondents strongly agree that they enrolled in the TVET to gain skills for self - employment. Those agreed as represented by 39.0 percent, 15.4 percent representing those who disagreed and 5.1 percent strongly disagreed. The item had a mean of 1.852 and a standard deviation of .8630. Therefore, most of the informants indicated that they do not enroll in the TVET to gain skills for self – employment but enrolled since they had no alternative options for enrolling in any other tertiary institution.

The results in table 2 indicate that most respondents at 60.7 percent strongly disagreed that the trainees enrolled in the TVET because they dropped out of school, 29.9 percent disagreed, and 4.8 percent agreed while those who strongly agreed at 4.5. The item had a mean of 3.468 and a standard deviation of 0.7870 indicating that majority of the respondents feel that the trainees do not enroll in the TVET because they dropped out of school.

The descriptive statistics results shown in table 2 reveal that trainees strongly disagreed at 32.9 percent that they enrolled in the TVET because they come from a poor family, 24.2 percent of them agreed, 22.7 percent strongly agreed while those who disagreed at 20.2. The item had a mean rating of 2.634 and standard deviation of 1.1609 an implication that majority of the respondents feel that they enrolled in the TVET because they come from a poor family.

The descriptive statistics results also indicate that respondents strongly disagree at 63.4 percent that they joined TVET to be preoccupied and grow, 16.9 percent of them disagreed, while those who strongly agreed at 11.2 percent and 8.5 percent agreed. The item had a mean of 3.326 and a standard deviation of 1.0310. Therefore, the descriptive statistics results making a conclusion that the trainees do not join TVET to be preoccupied and grow.

The descriptive analysis results shown in 4.11 indicate that 66.5 percent of the respondents strongly disagree that they joined TVET because they performed poorly in secondary school. Those disagreed as represented by 17.8 percent, 9.7 percent representing those who agreed and 6.0 percent strongly agreed. The item had a mean of 3.447 and a standard deviation of 0.8975. Therefore, most of the informants indicated that they joined TVET because they performed poorly in secondary school.

The results also indicate that respondents at 31.4 percent of informants agreed that they were encouraged by their parents to enroll in TVET, 31.1 percent disagreed, and 21.5 percent strongly agreed while those who strongly disagreed at 16.0. The item had a mean of 2.417 and a standard deviation of 0.9977 an indication that majority of the respondents feel they were encouraged by their parents to join TVET.

The results indicate that respondents at 31.4 percent of informants strongly agreed that their parents are aware of the presence of the TVETs and courses offered, 29.6 percent agreed, and 23.0 percent disagreed while those who strongly disagreed at 6.6. The item had a mean of 1.955 and a standard deviation of 0.9508 an indication that majority of the respondents feel their parents are not aware of the presence of the TVETs and courses offered.

Attitude of trainees pursuing higher TVET qualifications and enrolment

The researcher sought to find out whether the enrolled trainees were willing to pursue higher qualifications in the same course they were taking and their attitude towards TVET institutions so as to understand influence of the same on enrolment. The researcher intended to find out whether trainees had interest in whatever they were studying and their attitude towards TVETs. The findings are presented in Figure 2

Figure 2. Percentage willingness to pursue the same course to higher level

Majority of the respondents were willing to pursue the same course to higher level as represented by 93.96 percent while 6.04 percent were not willing. This means that given the opportunity, those who have graduated with a diploma would wish to do a degree. Since the TVETs do not offer degrees, the graduates move out and enroll in technical universities hence enrolment does

not increase. Willingness to pursue higher qualifications in the same course can be a boost to the enrolment if the TVETs are able to offer such opportunities for advancement without compromising the quality of the academic content and certification.

Trainees’ attitude on enrolling in TVET before and after being enrolled

The researcher sought to know trainees attitude towards TVETs before being enrolled into TVET and after enrolling in TVET so as to find out how attitude influences enrolment. The items required the trainees to indicate whether they enjoy being in TVET institution, whether TVET was their preferred choice of institution and whether they would recommend their colleagues to enroll in TVET. The results of responses to the items are presented in Table 3

Table 3. Percentage trainees’ positivity response and enrolment in TVET institutions

		Frequency	Percent
Do your fellow trainees enjoy being in a TVET Institute?	Yes	293	88.5
	No	38	11.5
Was TVET institution your preferred choice after you completed primary or secondary school?	Yes	141	42.6
	No	190	57.4
Would you recommend your colleagues to enroll in a TVET institution?	Yes	251	75.8
	No	80	24.2

Table 3 shows that, majority of the respondents involved in the study stated that their fellow trainees enjoy being in a TVET institute as indicated by 88.5 percent while 11.5 percent do not enjoy. This is an indication of change of attitude towards enrolling in TVETs after being enrolled. The change in attitude from negative to positive could lead into improved enrolment in TVETs in future. 57.4 percent of the informants revealed that TVET institutions were not their preferred choice after completing secondary school while 42.6 percent agreed that TVET institutions were their preferred choice of institution. This means that there is poor attitude towards TVET institutions in the communities and therefore trainees eventually find themselves enrolled in a TVET institution as a last result when they are unable to enroll in any other tertiary institution. Negative attitude could be one of the causes of low enrolment in TVETs as found out in this study.

The study findings indicated that, majority of the respondents were willing to recommend their colleagues to enroll in a TVET institution as represented by 75.8 percent while 24.2 percent were not. This was after they had enrolled and started learning as trainees that they realized the value of TVET institutions. This could result in improved enrolment in the long run. The TVET institutions’ stakeholders included are the principals, trainers, trainees and surrounding communities’ attitude has not completely changed positively to favour increased enrolment.

Null hypothesis stating and testing

The hypothesis in this study were tested based on trainees’ data because the trainees have first-hand information in understanding the determinants which influence their enrolment in TVETs and in various courses.

Testing hypothesis H04

The hypothesis in this study was tested based data collected from respondents on attitude of trainees and how the trainees’ attitude influences enrolment in TVETs.

H04: There is no significant relationship between trainees’ attitudes and enrolment of trainees’ in public TVETs in Nakuru County, Kenya.

Data collected from trainees on how their attitude influences their enrolment in TVETs was also analyzed using ANOVA test. The results are shown in Table 4

Table 4. One-way ANOVA test for trainees’ attitude and enrolment in TVETs

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
As a trainee I prefer theoretical work to practical work	Between Groups	.063	1	.063	.053	.819
	Within Groups	395.091	329	1.201		
	Total	395.154	330			
Given opportunity to join academic oriented courses, I would not have enrolled in TVET	Between Groups	2.052	1	2.052	2.770	.097
	Within Groups	243.737	329	.741		
	Total	245.789	330			
I enrolled in the TVET to gain skills for self - employment	Between Groups	.309	1	.309	.414	.521
	Within Groups	245.438	329	.746		
	Total	245.746	330			
I enrolled in the TVET because I dropped out of school	Between Groups	.500	1	.500	.807	.370
	Within Groups	203.917	329	.620		
	Total	204.417	330			
I enrolled in the TVET because I came from a poor family	Between Groups	4.810	1	4.810	3.597	.059
	Within Groups	439.957	329	1.337		
	Total	444.767	330			
I enrolled in TVET to be preoccupied and grow	Between Groups	5.410	1	5.410	5.154	.024
	Within Groups	345.351	329	1.050		
	Total	350.761	330			

I joined TVET because i performed poor in school	Between Groups	8.253	1	8.253	10.541	.001
	Within Groups	257.572	329	.783		
	Total	265.825	330			
I was encouraged by my parents to join TVET	Between Groups	.002	1	.002	.002	.967
	Within Groups	328.464	329	.998		
	Total	328.465	330			
Our parents are aware of the presence of the TVETs and courses offered	Between Groups	.203	1	.203	.224	.637
	Within Groups	298.118	329	.906		
	Total	298.320	330			

This hypothesis was tested as shown in Table 4 and from the analysis, it was concluded that, Since $p\text{-value} = 0.3883 > P\text{-value} = 0.05$, H_0 was not rejected and the conclusion made is that there is no statistically significant mean difference between trainees' attitudes and enrolment of trainees' in public TVETs as determined by one-way ANOVA ($F(1, 329) = 2.618, P = 0.3883$). This points out that, although there is negative publicity of TVETs by the community and prospective trainees parents or guardians due to other professions being viewed as well-paying than those trained in TVETs as opined by Aryeetey & Andoh (2011); Buyiaga, (2021) and Friedman & Mandel (2011), there is growing change in attitude which starts from the continuing trainees and the wave is penetrating the community shifting the status of the attitude of prospective trainees in Nakuru County to positive which may positively influence enrolment in TVETs in future.

CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

The study revealed that there is negative attitude of trainees towards TVETs evidenced by the fact that most trainees indicated they would not have joined TVET if they had scored a better grade. Scoring high grades of C+ and above negatively influences enrolment in TVETs. The findings show that the attitude towards the TVET institutions as a whole is the one which is negative but attitude towards the TVET courses on offer in the TVETS is positive. The trainees indicated that they are gaining important technical skills which will enable them to be employed by some companies or they can singly or jointly form "workshops" to provide services in the areas they trained in. The study finally concluded that there were a number of challenges facing TVETs which need attention for enrolment to increase and the TVET institutions to be fully utilized.

RECOMMENDATIONS OF THE STUDY

On the basis of the findings and conclusions of the study, a number of recommendations have been made. The researcher recommends that: -

To water down the negative attitude towards TVETS, let there be courses tailored specifically for trainees with quality grades of C+ and above so as to encourage them to enrol in TVETs. The courses can be taught in selected TVETS to begin with and affiliated to universities for examination and awarding of degree to improve the image of TVETS since universities are offering degrees in technical areas like engineering of different levels.

The TVETs' curriculum should be industry based and demand driven to ensure TVET graduates get employment as soon as they graduate. Review of remuneration of TVET graduates to be at par with that of academic oriented careers or even higher to attract

more prospective trainees. The skill development system in Kenya follows a curriculum based, time bound approach as opposed to demand driven approach and certification is based on completion of courses rather than demonstration of competency. Therefore a shift from this tradition would be in favour of increased enrolment in TVET institutions.

TVET institutions market themselves through social media by publishing success stories from the TVET graduates obtained through tracer studies and have exhibitions and awarding fares for leading innovative graduates practicing in the communities for those already in secondary school to emulate and make informed decision to pursue careers in TVETS. This will change the image of TVETs totally

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Cite this Article: Benard Kyalo Makato, Mercy M. Mugambi, Jeremiah M. Kalai (2022). Individual and Institutional Determinants of Trainees' Enrolment in Public Technical Vocational Education and Training Institutions in Nakuru County, Kenya. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 5(9), 3486-3501